

FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF OPTICAL FIBER SENSOR EMBEDDED IN SMART COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

Tae Seong Jang¹, Jung Ju Lee¹, Dong Chun Lee¹, Dae Cheol Seo¹ and Ho Kim²

¹*Department of Mechanical Engineering, Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology, 373-1, Kusong-dong, Yuseong-gu, Taejeon, 305-701, Korea*

²*KIA Motors Corp. R&D Center, 781-1, Soha-dong, Kwang myung-shi, Kyungki-do, 423-701, Korea*

SUMMARY: Fatigue behavior of the optical fiber sensors embedded in composite laminate was studied. The fatigue life of the embedded optical fiber was investigated by measuring the intensity change of the laser signal transmitted through it. Test specimens consisted of three types of stacking sequences; $[0_6/OF/0_6]_T$, $[0_2/90_4/OF/90_4/0_2]_T$ and $[0_3/90_3/OF/90_3/0_3]_T$. From the experiment, it was observed that the optical fiber sensor embedded in composite laminate under fatigue loading was fractured at lower stress level than the average static stress at which the fracture of the embedded optical fiber within the laminate occurred. It was found that the fatigue life of the optical fiber embedded in cross-ply laminate was closely related with the growth of transverse matrix crack. On the other hand, the fatigue fracture of the embedded optical fiber within the unidirectional-ply laminate occurred due to the growth of internal defects of optical fiber. The decrease in fatigue life of the optical fiber embedded in the unidirectional-ply laminate is relatively small compared to the cross-ply laminate case.

KEYWORDS: optical fiber sensor, smart composite structures, fatigue behavior, S-N curve, transverse matrix crack, internal defects, strain concentration, laser signal intensity

INTRODUCTION

There was a considerable increase in the use of composite materials for aerospace, marine and other structural applications because of their high specific stiffness and strength. However, periodical and careful inspection are required due to the limiting features of composite laminates such as transverse matrix cracking and delamination. Recently, smart structure concepts have been applied to composite structures for the effective monitoring of structural integrity. Optical fiber sensor technology has been used for the purpose of monitoring the integrity of composite materials. One such application is that of embedding optical fibers into composite materials. The increasing use of optical fiber sensor as a sensing material has been found because they have several attractive features compared to other sensors [1]. Optical fiber sensors offer following capabilities to smart structures such as structural health monitoring, internal deformation measurement, impact detection, vibration sensing, etc. The effect of the embedded optical fiber on the mechanical behavior of host composite structures was studied. Jensen et al. [2, 3] and Measures et al. [4] reported that embedded optical fibers may degrade the uniaxial tensile and compressive properties of composite laminates. Singh et al. [5] measured the strain of composite material around the embedded optical fiber whose diameters and coating states are different from each other. Seo et al. [6] measured the damage caused by the embedding of optical fiber in terms of the transverse matrix crack density of

cross-ply laminate. Lee et al. [7] performed qualitative investigation on the fatigue behavior of composite laminate with the embedded optical fiber sensor.

However, for the successful application of optical fiber sensor to smart composite structures, in addition to the integrity of the composite laminate with embedded optical fibers, it should be also checked whether the embedded optical fiber sensor can survive and perform their designed functions under the service loading condition of host structures. The structures in service are usually subjected to variable random loading and the materials under fatigue loading are generally fractured at lower stress level than that under static loading. Therefore, it should be investigated whether the embedded optical fiber sensor performs their designed function under the given loading condition. In this paper, the fatigue behavior of optical fiber sensor embedded in composite laminate was investigated. The composite laminate specimens consisted of three types of stacking sequences; a unidirectional-ply laminate $[0_{12}]_T$, and two cross-ply laminates $[0_2/90_4]_S$ and $[0_3/90_3]_S$. One optical fiber was embedded in the neutral plane of each specimen along the loading direction. With these specimens, comparison of the fatigue behavior of the optical fiber embedded in different laminates was performed by measuring fatigue life of each specimen and obtaining the S-N curve.

SPECIMEN FABRICATION

All specimens were fabricated by glass/epoxy prepreg. SUNKYUNG INDUSTRY Co. UGN-150 prepreg was used. The glass/epoxy laminates have the advantage that we can directly observe the bleeding of laser, the initiation and the growth of damage in the specimen, such as delamination, splitting and transverse crack, due to their transparency. Fig. 1 shows three types of stacking sequences, the location and orientation of the embedded optical fiber. The nominal thickness of all specimens is 1.2mm. Optical fibers were embedded in the neutral plane of laminate by using the fiber positioning jig designed to make it easy to align them with the loading direction. The 60mm test section part of the optical fiber coating was removed chemically by acetone to increase the sensitivity to damage.

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram of specimen configuration with embedded optical fiber

Fig. 2: Geometry of specimen (dimensions in millimeters)

After the laminate was cured in the programmable autoclave along the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle, the HANKOOK FIBER Co. HFG GU-300 E-glass loading tabs were attached at both ends by using CYANAMID FM 73 film adhesive. Then the specimens

were cutted out by using a water-cooled diamond wheel cutter. The final shape of a specimen is shown in Fig. 2.

EXPERIMENTAL

The fatigue tests were performed by using 25ton MTS servohydraulic test machine. Fatigue tests were carried out under load control with a sinusoidal waveform at frequency of 5Hz and stress ratio, R (=minimum stress/maximum stress), of 0.1. The laser was introduced into the optical fiber sensor embedded in composite laminate by using a coupler which was composed of a set of lenses and an optical fiber positioning assembly. The intensity of the laser transmitted through the embedded optical fiber was measured by a photo-diode. Load history and laser intensity signal were recorded automatically during test by using a PC-based data acquisition system. The overall experimental setup is shown schematically in Fig. 3. The fracture of optical fiber was detected by the intensity drop-off of the laser signal transmitted through it and visually confirmed by the bleeding of the laser signal at the location of its fracture. With this experimental setup, we investigated the fatigue life of the optical fiber sensor embedded in composite laminate under the various levels of fatigue loads and then plotted the S-N curve.

Fig. 3: Schematic diagram of experimental setup

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fatigue behavior of the optical fiber embedded in unidirectional-ply laminate

Fatigue tests for the optical fiber embedded in unidirectional-ply laminate were conducted under various maximum stress levels with the stress ratio, R , of 0.1 to avoid the compressive stress during the fatigue loading. The fracture of optical fiber was detected by observing the change of laser intensity transmitted through it. Fig. 4 shows the typical change of the laser intensity for unidirectional-ply laminate specimen as fatigue cycles increase. As can be seen in this figure, the laser intensity is nearly uniform until the fracture of optical fiber. This laser signal behavior shown in Fig. 4 means that the fracture of optical fiber sensor occurred abruptly without gradual damage accumulation in the embedded optical fiber sensor. To make

certain of this, the specimen was examined macroscopically and microscopically. In macroscopic observations, any evidence was not found for the fracture of reinforcement glass fibers or the internal cracking such as matrix cracks or delaminations until the fracture of optical fiber sensor. In microscopic observations, the debonding between the optical fiber and the matrix, which can cause the fracture of the brittle optical fiber by generating the shear stress in the optical fiber, was not found. The microscopic views around the fractured optical fiber are shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 4: Laser signal intensity of the unidirectional-ply

The laser intensity drops rapidly when the optical fiber is fractured and then decreases gradually. The gradual decrease of laser intensity is caused by additional fractures at other positions of the optical fiber in the test section and subsequent cracking from the first fracture, as can be seen in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Microscopic pictures of a failed optical fibre in $[0_6/OF/0_6]_T$, (b) is the magnified photo of Part A in (a)

In these tests, the fatigue fracture of the embedded optical fiber sensor was determined when the abrupt drop-off of laser signal intensity occurred, as shown in Fig. 4. Then the S-N curve was plotted from the cycles at that time as shown in Fig. 6. In this figure, it is not easy to characterize the fatigue behavior of the embedded optical fiber because of wide scatter. Generally, the strength of fibrous materials such as reinforcement glass fibers and optical fibers can not have a unique value due to the inhomogeneous distribution of internal defects within the fiber. The wide scatter means the variety of sizes and locations of internal defects. In Fig. 6, the ordinate axis represents the ratio of maximum fatigue stress applied to laminate with respect to the average static stress at which the embedded optical fiber within the laminate occurred.

Fig 6: Fatigue life of the optical fiber in $[0_6/OF/0_6]_T$

From these results, it can be said that the optical fiber embedded in unidirectional-ply laminate has relatively good fatigue resistance and the optical fiber embedded in unidirectional-ply laminate is fractured due to the growth of its internal defects under fatigue loading.

Fatigue behavior of the optical fiber embedded in cross-ply laminate

In the above fatigue tests, no defects or damages in the unidirectional-ply laminate were observed until the fracture of optical fiber. In fatigue tests of the optical fiber embedded in cross-ply laminate, a matrix cracking in the transverse plies always preceded the fracture of the embedded optical fiber. After curing, there might exist a number of inherent microcracks in the matrix of the cross-ply laminate. These microcracks, particularly in the transverse plies, grow along the direction of reinforcement fibers as fatigue cycles are increased. A crack that grows faster than others fractures the optical fiber. Because the matrix crack causes the strain concentration, the embedded optical fiber is fractured in a few cycles after the matrix crack arrives at the optical fiber. One noticeable fact is that the embedded optical fiber is fractured just by the matrix crack which arrives at the optical fiber first. In the previous study [8] concerning the fracture of cross-ply laminate with embedded optical fiber under static tensile loading, a lot of matrix cracks were observed until the fracture of optical fiber. However, under fatigue loading, the strain concentration makes a direct cause of the fracture of optical fiber. From the microscopic observations, it can be said that the matrix crack causes the fracture of optical fiber directly, as shown in Fig. 7. The fatigue behavior for two cross-ply laminates $[0_2/90_4/OF/90_4/0_2]$ and $[0_3/90_3/OF/90_3/0_3]$, is shown in Fig. 8. The S-N curves of

optical fibers also show similar trend to those of conventional metals. The fatigue limits of optical fibers embedded in two cross-ply laminates are about 30% value of average static tensile stress at which the embedded optical fiber within the laminate occurred. Fig. 9 shows the fatigue life of optical fiber embedded in different laminates where the ordinate axis represents the maximum stress applied to laminates under fatigue loading.

Fig. 7: Microscopic pictures of a failed optical fiber in cross-ply laminate, (b) is the magnified photo of part A in (a)

Fig 8: Fatigue life of optical fibers in cross-ply laminates

Fig. 9: Fatigue life of optical fibers embedded in different laminates

From these results, it can be said that the strain concentration by the matrix crack causes the fracture of the optical fiber embedded in cross-ply laminate under the fatigue loading. The growth of matrix crack by the fatigue loading can be estimated by the fatigue life of the optical fiber embedded in cross-ply laminate, which is initiated from the free edge. It can be also said that the optical fiber has lower fatigue resistance when embedded in cross-ply laminate than unidirectional-ply laminate. Therefore, smart composite structures under fatigue loading should be designed to ensure the integrity of the embedded optical fiber sensor for the successful applications.

Fatigue behavior of the optical fiber embedded in laminates with different gage length

In this study, the gage length of all specimens is 60mm. Generally, the fibrous materials have different strengths depending on their length. So comparisons of present result with the previous results [8] for 120mm gage length specimens were performed. Fig. 10 is the result for the unidirectional-ply laminate specimens and Fig. 11 is for the cross-ply laminate specimens.

Fig. 10: Fatigue life of optical fibers with

Fig. 11: Fatigue life of optical fibers with

In Fig. 10, we can observe the apparent drop of the fatigue life of the optical fiber with 120mm gage length. This is due to the increase of defects within optical fiber. The scatter is due to the inhomogeneous distribution of defects. In unidirectional-ply laminate, the gage length is very important factor affecting the fatigue life of the embedded optical fiber. However, in cross-ply laminate, the two curves are nearly identical as shown in Fig. 11. This is due to the difference of the fracture mechanism. In other words, the optical fiber under fatigue loading is fractured by the growth of its internal defects when embedded in the unidirectional-ply laminate, while by the strain concentration due to the matrix crack when embedded in the cross-ply laminate. So, the dependence of the fatigue life on the gage length is not found in case of the cross-ply laminate.

CONCLUSIONS

From this study for the fatigue behavior of embedded optical fiber sensors within the composite laminates, the following conclusions were obtained.

1. The optical fiber sensor embedded in laminate under fatigue loading is fractured at lower stress level than the average static stress at which the fracture of the embedded optical fiber within the laminate occurred. The optical fiber, especially embedded in cross-ply laminate, has very low fatigue resistance. Thus, for the successful application of optical fiber sensor to smart composite structures, this point should be carefully considered in the design process.
2. The decrease in fatigue life of optical fiber is relatively small when embedded in unidirectional-ply laminate compared to cross-ply laminate. The optical fiber embedded in unidirectional-ply laminate is fractured by the fatigue damage due to the growth of its internal defects. The optical fiber embedded in cross-ply laminate is fractured by the strain concentration produced at the tip of the primary matrix crack.
3. The fatigue life of optical fiber sensor is not dependent on the gage length when embedded in cross-ply laminate. The matrix crack is the dominant factor affecting the fatigue life of the optical fiber sensor embedded in cross-ply laminate.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank KOSEF (Korea Science and Engineering Foundation) for the financial support for this work under the contract No. 96-0200-05-01-3.

REFERENCES

1. Claus, R.O., "Overview of Fiber Optic Sensor-based Smart Materials and Structures", *Proceedings of the Conference on Optical Fiber Sensor-based Smart Materials and Structures*, held at Blacksburg, Virginia, 1991, p. 3.

2. Jensen, D.W., Pascual, J. and August, J.A., "Performance of a Graphite/bismaleimide Laminates with Embedded Optical Fibers. Part I: Uniaxial Tension", *Smart Materials and Structures*, Vol. 1, 1992, pp. 24 - 30.
3. Jensen, D.W., Pascual, J. and August, J.A., "Performance of a Graphite/bismaleimide Laminates with Embedded Optical Fibers. Part I: Uniaxial Compression", *Smart Materials and Structures*, Vol. 1, 1992, pp. 31 -35.
4. Measures, R.M., Glossop, N.D.W., Lymer, J., Leblanc, M., West, M., Dubois, S., Tsaw, W. and Tennyson, R.C., "Structurally Integrated Fiber Optic Damage Assessment System for Composite Materials", *Applied Optics*, Vol. 28, No. 13, 1989, pp. 2626 -2633.
5. Singh, H., Sirkis, J.S. and Dasgupta, A., "Micro-interaction of Optical Fibers Embedded in Laminated Composites", *Proceedings of SPIE Fiber Optic Smart Structures and Skins*, Vol. 1588, 1991, p. 76.
6. Seo, D.C. and Lee, J.J., "Effect of Embedded Optical Fibers on Matrix Crack Spacing in Smart Structures", *Composite Structures*, Vol. 32, 1995, pp. 51 -58.
7. Lee, D.C., Lee, J.J. and Yun, S.J., "The Mechanical Characteristics of Smart Composite Structures with Embedded Optical Fiber Sensors", *Composite Structures*, Vol. 32, 1995, pp. 39 -50.
8. Lee, D.C. and Lee, J.J., "Fatigue Behavior of Composite Structures with Embedded Optical Fiber Sensors", *Proceedings of the Tenth International Conference on Composite Materials*, Vol. 5, 1995, pp. 307 -314.